

ANGINA PECTORIS

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Abstract: *Angina (Greek stenós - "narrow, small, weak" + kardía - "heart") (old Latin angina pectoris) is a clinical syndrome characterized by a feeling of discomfort or discomfort behind the chest.*

Pain occurs suddenly after a meal, during physical exertion or emotional stress, usually irradiates the left shoulder, neck, lower jaw, between the shoulders, the area under the left shoulder and lasts for 10-15 minutes. The pain disappears when physical activity is stopped or after a short-acting nitrate intake (e.g., sublingual nitroglycerin injection). The clinical picture of angina was first described by William Hayden.

CAUSES OF DEVELOPMENT OF ANGENCARDIA

Angina pectoris develops due to a lack of acute blood supply to the coronary arteries, which occurs when the blood supply to the heart and its blood demand are disproportionate. The result of acute coronary insufficiency is a myocardial infarction, which leads to disruption of oxidative processes in the myocardium and excessive accumulation of unoxidized metabolic products (milk, pyruvic acid, coal and phosphoric acid) and other metabolites.

The most common cause of angina is coronary artery atherosclerosis. Rarely, angina pectoris develops as a result of infectious and infectious-allergic lesions.

Angina attacks are caused by emotional and physical stress.

Factors influencing the occurrence and development of angina are divided into variable and non-variable factors.

Factors that cannot be changed include age, gender, and genetic predisposition. Factors that can be changed include:

- Hyperlipidemia;
- Obesity;
- Hypo dynamics (inactivity);
- Smoking;

Arterial hypertension;
Anemia and intoxications;
Diabetes mellitus;
Increased relative viscosity of blood;
Psych emotional stress.

SYMPTOMS AND SYMPTOMS OF ANGINA

Most patients with angina experience discomfort or pain in the chest area. Discomfort is usually depressing, irritating, and burning. Often such patients place a fist or open palm on their chest in an attempt to describe the area of discomfort. Often the pain spreads to the inner surface of the left shoulder and left arm, neck; in rare cases - between the left teeth, jaw, shoulder blades, as well as the epigastric area, which may be accompanied by dipeptic disorders (heartburn, nausea, colic). In very rare cases, the pain may be localized only in the epigastric area or even in the head area, making it very difficult to diagnose.

Angina attacks usually begin with physical exertion, strong emotional arousal, overeating, being in a low-temperature environment, or high blood pressure. In these cases, the heart muscle requires more oxygen than it can pass through the narrowed coronary arteries. Stenosis of the coronary arteries, in the absence of their spasm or thrombosis, by chest pain associated with physical activity or other conditions that increase the oxygen demand of the heart muscle, aortic regurgitation or dysplastic cardiomyopathy, hypertrophic cardiomyopathy, aortic valve stenosis may also occur in patients with marked left ventricular hypertrophy.

An angina attack usually lasts 1 to 15 minutes. It disappears when stress is relieved or short-acting nitrates (sublingual nitroglycerin) are taken.

TREATMENT OF ANGINA

Objectives of treatment of angina:

Improving disease outcome by preventing myocardial infarction and death;

Reduce or eliminate symptoms.

LIFESTYLE CHANGE

Changing the patient's lifestyle is important to achieve the first goal. Improving the prognosis of the disease can be achieved through the following measures:

Quit smoking;

Moderate physical activity;

Diet and weight loss: Limit salt and saturated fats, and eat fruits, vegetables, and fish regularly.

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